

The Influence of Exchange Rate Fluctuation on the Economic Growth in Cambodia

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Abstract: Economic growth is closely linked to exchange rate dynamics, as fluctuations in currency values can significantly influence a country's economic performance. This research aims to investigate the impact of the exchange rate fluctuations and economic growth in Cambodia to determine the extent at which exchange rate fluctuations influence economic growth between 2019 and 2024 in Cambodian. Secondary data on gross domestic product (GDP) were obtained from International Monetary Fund, and the National Bank of Cambodia. The findings indicate a significant negative relationship between exchange rate fluctuations and economic growth during the study period. This suggests that variations in the exchange rate had an adverse effect on economic growth. However, the analysis also showed that the exchange rate itself did not have a statistically significant impact on economic growth. Additionally, the results revealed a weak and statistically insignificant positive relationship between inflation and economic growth.

Keywords: Exchange Rate, Fluctuation, Inflation Rate, and Economic Growth in Cambodia

I. INTRODUCTION

Economic growth refers to the improvement in the production of goods and services within an economy. It is often defined as the rise in the inflation-adjusted market value of goods and services produced over a certain period. This growth typically happens due to increases in capital goods, the labor force, technological advancements, and human capital development. It is commonly measured by indicators like Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which reflects the total market value of additional goods and services produced. When the amount of physical capital in an economy increases and boosts labor productivity, economic growth is said to occur. However, sustained, and meaningful economic growth is not possible without a stable exchange rate.

According to International Monetary Fund (IMF) Glossary "exchange rate" is the price of one currency in terms of another. Most commonly, exchange rates are expressed as the number of units of domestic currency that will purchase one unit of foreign currency (e.g., units of currency per U.S. dollar). The exchange rate is the value at which one nation's currency can be traded for the currency of another country. It represents the cost of one currency in terms of another. This rate influences the comparative prices of local and international goods and plays a key role in determining a country's participation and competitiveness in global trade. Hong NGUYEN et al. (2021) investigated that the exchange rate is considered a tool improving the volume of exports and reducing imports. Also, the exchange rate plays a key role in determining prices in global trade. When a currency's value fluctuates, it can influence the cost of goods exchanged in that currency (Andrew Alderman et al., 2023).

The exchange rates fluctuation are vital to the operation of modern economies, as they affect multiple aspects of economic activity, including trade and investment (Lim, 2025). Particularly, Cambodia has adopted a managed floating exchange rate system for almost three decades, offers a valuable case study for policymakers and investors aiming to understand the complexities of exchange rate dynamics, particularly under varying economic conditions. Understanding how exchange rates fluctuate across different economic states is essential. A thorough analysis of the likelihood of transitions between these states as well as the characteristics of each individual state is critical for gaining a deeper and more complete insight.

The behavior of the nominal exchange rate between the Khmer riel and the US dollar under varying market conditions has yet to be thoroughly examined in Cambodia. Studying exchange rate patterns across different

market environments is crucial for several reasons. As a developing country heavily reliant on trade, gaining such insights can support policymakers in formulating strategies aimed at controlling inflation and promoting sustainable economic growth. The National Bank of Cambodia (NBC) recognizes the need to analyze the exchange rate - inflation relationship under dollarization as a structural issue in light of the experience of the Cambodian economy during the global crisis period, and to explore possible policy directions (Chung, 2017).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The exchange rate policy of Cambodia is a critical component of its macroeconomic framework, shaped by the country's unique economic context and the widespread use of the US dollar alongside its domestic currency, the Cambodian Riel. This literature review examines key scholarly and institutional contributions to understanding Cambodia's exchange rate regime, its impacts, and ongoing policy challenges.

2.1 An Overview of Exchange Rate Fluctuation in Cambodia

The National Bank of Cambodia (NBC), serving as the country's monetary authority, has consistently emphasized that maintaining price stability relies on a stable exchange rate between the Khmer Riel and the US dollar (Lim, 2023). Furthermore, Lim (2023) reveals that to manage exchange rate fluctuations in the local foreign exchange market, the NBC controls the money supply, focusing especially on the circulation of the Riel within the domestic economy. Also, The NBC emphasizes efforts to promote the use of the Riel to gradually reduce dollar dependency that fostering a robust domestic currency can enhance financial sector development and monetary sovereignty (NBC, 2022).

According to Lim, (2023), investigated that the NBC aims to stabilize exchange rate fluctuations between the Khmer Riel and the US Dollar in the local foreign exchange market. To achieve this, it uses a method known as the US Dollar Auction. This involves buying or selling US Dollars from money changers within the domestic market to regulate the amount of Riel in circulation. The phenomenon of dollarization in Cambodia is extensively documented. Dollarization has facilitated trade and investment but also limited monetary policy independence. However, such a high level of dollarization makes Cambodia's monetary policy strongly connected with changes in the U.S. Federal Funds Rate, and the evidence of such a relationship has been shown in Duma (2011) and Samreth et al. (2019). A managed peg to the USD has contributed to relatively inflation rates and exchange rate stability, which in turn supports foreign direct investment (FDI) and economic growth (Saly & Satrianto, 2024). Dollarization has helped insulate the economy from local currency volatility, an issue common in emerging markets. However, the policy also poses challenges.

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

Exchange rate refers to the value at which one country's currency can be traded for another's. It represents the price of one currency in terms of another. Hossain (2002) stated that exchange rate plays a vital role in linking the price systems of two countries, facilitating international trade, and influencing the levels of imports and exports, along with the nation's balance of payments. Similarly, Matthew (2020) argued that flexible exchange rate regimes tend to be more beneficial for developing countries.

At the same vein, Aliyu (2009) emphasized that an appreciation of the exchange rate leads to a rise in imports and a decline in exports, whereas a depreciation encourages exports and reduces imports. Exchange rate depreciation also promotes a shift in consumer preference from foreign to locally produced goods. As a result, income is redirected from importing nations to exporting ones due to changes in the terms of trade, which in turn affects the economic growth of both exporting and importing countries.

Previous studies examining the effect of exchange rates on economic growth have produced mixed findings. Some empirical research suggests that fluctuations in the real exchange rate can influence economic performance. For example, (Edwards et al., 2005) found that countries with more flexible exchange rate regimes tend to experience faster economic growth. Similarly, Hausmann et al. (2005) reported that real exchange rate depreciation is positively linked to higher growth. Rodrik (2008) further argued that real undervaluation of the exchange rate supports economic growth by increasing the profitability of the tradable sector and expanding its share in the domestic economy. He explained that in developing countries, the tradable sector is often relatively small due to being more vulnerable to institutional weaknesses and market inefficiencies compared to the non-tradable sector. In this context, real exchange rate undervaluation serves as a second-best policy tool to offset these challenges, improve profitability, encourage investment, and ultimately stimulate economic growth.

Aghion et al. (2009) reported similar findings, noting that while real exchange rate volatility negatively impacts economic growth, this effect diminishes in countries with more advanced financial systems. Similarly, Akpan (2009) explored the foreign exchange market and economic growth in Nigeria, an emerging oil-dependent economy, over the period 1970–2003, and discovered a positive correlation between exchange rate and economic growth. In another study, Obansa et al. (2013) examined the exchange rate–growth relationship in Nigeria from 1970 to 2010, concluding that exchange rate had a significant impact on economic growth and that exchange rate liberalization contributed positively to Nigeria's economic performance. Azeez et al. (2012) also assessed the

influence of exchange rate volatility on Nigeria's macroeconomic performance between 1986 and 2010, finding a positive relationship between exchange rate and GDP. In contrast, Umoru & Eborieme (2013) using an error correction model, argued that trade liberalization enhanced industrial sector growth and stabilized the exchange rate market between 1970 and 2010. They observed a significant positive correlation between the trade liberalization and industrial growth in Nigeria. In the short run, a 10 per cent rise in trade liberalization lagged one, two and three periods stimulate industrial production by 1.55, 1.09 and 1.23 percent, respectively.

Barkoulas et al. (2002) investigated how exchange rate fluctuations influence trade volume and variability, concluding that exchange rate volatility hampers trade expansion and reduces its potential benefits. Eichengreen & Leblang (2003) conducted a study across 12 countries spanning 120 years and found a strong negative relationship between exchange rate stability and economic growth. However, they emphasized that such results are highly sensitive to the time frame and the sample used in the analysis.

2.3 Hypotheses and Research Framework

- H1: There will be significant relationship between exchange rate and economic growth
- H2: There will be significant relationship between inflation rate and economic growth

IVs

Exchange Rate Fluctuation

DV

Figure 1: Research Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to the study conducted by Bringula et al. (2017), the researchers adopted descriptive survey research design. Data on Cambodia gross domestic product (GDP), exchange rate and inflation rate were collected from National Bank of Cambodia (NBC), Annual Report, and IMF between 2019 and 2024. According to (Dahami, 2024) and Wooditch et al. (2021), the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method is a fundamental statistical technique used to estimate linear regression models by minimizing the sum of the squared differences between observed and predicted values. This approach effectively determines the relationship between dependent and independent variables and is widely applied in both statistics and machine learning for building predictive models. Moreover, According to Mallik et al. (2011) explained that a p-value less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) indicates a statistically significant deviation from the baseline regression function, signaling the presence of a threshold. Conversely, a p-value greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$) suggests insufficient evidence to detect such a threshold, meaning the regression function does not significantly differ from its baseline in that region.

Pearson's product moment correlation were used to analyse the data (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). And according to Frost (2021), a p-value greater than 0.05 indicates that the correlation is not statistically significant, and thus there is insufficient evidence of a linear association between the variables by using SPSS 26.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Table 1 shows The GDP growth rate exhibits notable volatility over the period, ranging from a high of 7.1% in 2019 to a sharp contraction of -3.1% in 2020, reflecting the economic impact of global disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The negative growth in 2020 represents the lowest point in the series and marks a significant deviation from the preceding year’s high growth trajectory.

Following 2020, the economy rebounded with positive growth each subsequent year: 3.0% in 2021, 5.0% in 2022, 5.4% in 2023, and 5.5% in 2024, indicating a gradual and sustained recovery.

The exchange rate remains relatively stable over the six-year period, fluctuating within a narrow band between 4055 and 4110 KHR/USD. The exchange rate peaked in 2023 (4110) and then declined slightly to 4071 in 2024. Table 1 shows the inflation rate exhibits moderate variability, peaking at 5.4% in 2022—likely due to post-pandemic supply chain constraints and global price pressures—before sharply declining to 0.8% in 2024.

The inflation rate displays greater variability than the exchange rate but less than GDP growth. The highest inflation was observed in 2022 at 5.4%, coinciding with global inflationary pressures, while the lowest was in 2024 at 0.8%, reflecting successful inflation containment measures as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Cambodia gross domestic product (GDP) growth rate, exchange rate and inflation rate

Years	GDP Annual Growth Rate in %	Average Annual Exchange Rate	Average Annual Inflation Rate
2019	7.1	4055	1.9
2020	-3.1	4093	2.9
2021	3.0	4099	2.9
2022	5.0	4102	5.4
2023	5.4	4110	2.1
2024	5.5	4071	0.8

Annual Report of National Bank of Cambodia and IMF

Figure 2: GDP, Exchange Rate, and Inflation Rate

Hypotheses Tested

H1: There will be significant relationship between exchange rate and economic growth

Table 2: Relationship between exchange rate and economic growth

Model	Sum of Squares	d f	Mean Square	F	Si g.
Regression	7.568	1	7.568	0.5 18	0.5 12
Residual	58.460	4	14.615		
Total	66.028	5			

R= 0.339
R Square = 0.115
Adjust R Square = - 0.107
Std. Error of the Estimate = 3.8230

Table 2 shows the regression analysis investigating the impact of exchange rate on economic growth reveals no statistically significant relationship ($F(1,4) = 0.518$, $p = 0.512 > 0.05$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) suggests that the exchange rate accounts for only about 11.5% of the variation in economic growth while the remaining 88.5% may be influenced by other external factors not included in the current model. However, the adjusted R^2 of - 0.107 indicates that the model's explanatory power is inferior to that of a null model with no predictors, signifying poor fit. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.339$) reflects a weak positive linear association, which lacks statistical and practical significance. These findings support the retention of the null hypothesis, suggesting that exchange rate movements do not meaningfully predict economic growth in this context. This is in line with the findings of (Morina et al., 2020).

H2: There will be significant relationship between inflation rate and economic growth

Table 3: Relationship between inflation rate and economic growth

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Si g.
Regression	2.195	1	2.195	0.1 38	0.7 30
Residual	63.833	4	15.958		
Total	66.028	5			

R= 0.182
R Square = 0.033
Adjust R Square = - 0.208
Std. Error of the Estimate = 3.9948

Table 3 shows the regression analysis results between the inflation rate and economic growth. The findings indicate that the relationship between these two variables is not statistically significant ($F(1,4) = 0.138$; $\text{Adj } R^2 = - 0.208$; $p = 0.730 > 0.05$), leading to the retention of the null hypothesis. To further explore this relationship, the table reports the coefficient of determination, $R^2 = 0.033$, suggests that only approximately 3.3% of the variance in economic growth can be explained by the inflation rate while the remaining 96.7% may be influenced by other external factors not included in the current model. Moreover, the adjusted $R^2 = - 0.208$ implies that the model fits the data poorly and that the inclusion of the predictor (inflation rate) reduces the explanatory power compared to a model with no predictors at all. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.182$) also reflects a very weak positive linear relationship between inflation and economic growth, though it is not statistically or practically meaningful. This is in line with the findings of (Becha et al., 2023).

V. CONCLUSION, LIMITATION OF STUDY, AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In this study, we examined the effects of exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth over a six-year period, from 2019 to 2024. The persistent depreciation of the Riel against the US dollar in recent years prompted the formulation of the research problem. Data were sourced from the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the National Bank of Cambodia's statistical database, among others. From results obtained, it was found that there was a negatively significant relationship between exchange rate fluctuation, and economic growth during the period considered. This result revealed that exchange rate no statistically significant relationship with economic growth. Furthermore, it was found that there is an insignificant positive relationship between inflation rate and economic growth.

Despite several contributions provided in this study and provided support for hypothesized the significant relationship between exchange rate fluctuation and economic growth, there are some

limitations highlighted that form option for future researchers such as small sample size, use nonlinear regression and geographic context may limit the applicability.

This study was carried out on the influence exchange rate fluctuation and economic growth in Cambodia. Further studies can be conducted on the impact of domestic investment level and Foreign Direct Investment on economic growth in Cambodia.

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